

Humanize AI Tool: An Aid or Challenge for Education Industry

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Abstract – In the milieu, when AI turns as a pervasive technology touching every horizon of human life, untap its potential in making thriving revolutions in the field of education, pedagogy, andragogy, research and other areas of content creation is crucial to foster improved learning and innovation in the respective aforesaid field. Today almost every academicians, student, freelancer, content creator, blogger, columnist, copywriter, social media marketer, digital professionals, UI designers and all the other members of slack community uses one or more AI-based tools, to ease our day to day operations. Especially if we talked about the field of academics and research, the application of AI is common, but the issue of plagiarism is a big concern. To save much of our research time and to avoid the plagiarism problem detected by online AI plagiarism detectors, many people utilizes its bypassing technology such as Humanize AI or online paraphrasing tools.

In this research paper, the entire focus is on the revolution & challenges brought by AI and Humanize AI in the field of education, research, academics, and content creation. For the purpose of our research study, we collected primary data from 247 respondents in Uttar Pradesh. The paper has presented the findings, suggestions as well as the conclusion, which will become a ground for the future researchers to use upon. The research paper tries to clarify both the aid and challenging side of the Humanize AI presenting fact-driven balanced approach. So that, readers as well as future researchers can make a clear opinion about this respective AI technologies and concentrate on extending future contribution of study in this area and its inter-related field.

Keywords: AI, Humanize AI, Paraphrasing, AI Content, Plagiarism, AI detector, Academics, GPT.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the words of Albert Einstein, "It has become appallingly obvious that our technology has exceeded our humanity". Obviously there is no lie to the fact that 21st century human has been highly dependent on AI based technological innovation surrounding him. Although the application of Artificial Intelligence is pervasive in multi-disciplinary aspect. And the field of education, research and content creation is also not the untouched one with its application. Today the education industry is flooded with millions of AI assistant tools, Chatbots, generative AI tools and other machine learning technology items.

All these AI tools and assistance are at one point empowering the stakeholders of the education industry, at the same time impeding human cognitive, intuition and creativity due to over-reliance. AI is used in education sector in multiple ways, focusing on students and teachers as well as the institution point of view. The way AI is getting deeply inclined with the education sector, unpredictable changes in education is expected. The rapidly changing pace of AI technology will definitely revamp the status and role of education industry in the years to come (Holmes & Tuomi, 2022).

Since technology is always a curiosity cynosure for the human mind. Every stakeholder of education industry is taking keen interest in using AI based tools like ChatGPT, Co-pilot, Claude, Deep Seek, Meta AI, Gemini, and so on to ease their day to day task. According to the report from Statista (March, 2024), the market size of Generative AI is projected to reach USD 62.7 Billion in 2025. Another Statista report titled, "ChatGPT Leads an Already Crowded Market", (November, 2023) claims that ChatGPT hold 19.7% of estimated share of worldwide users by AI text generation tool in 2022. Among the total market share of all these generative AI tools include the users from the area of academics, research and content creation sectors as well. From students to teachers, these AI Chatbots, generative AI assistance are preferable choice. The Students are also found generally satisfied with the ChatGPT in extending their writing skills. But at the same point of time, this generative AI technology is not challenge free. Thus responsible use of this AI assistant is recommendable. There is no doubt of the fact that it is another valuable tool from the family of AI, but judicious usage is suggestable (AI-Sofi, 2024).

1.1 AI tools in Academics

From teaching to learning, today every aspect of the education industry is tech-driven. Technology has become the part and parcel of the academics and its every stakeholders. Smartphone and the easy availability of internet connections empowered every student, teacher as well as the educational institutions to make use of Artificial Intelligence and AI based assistant tools and chat bots. From voice assistance to e-learning to intelligent tutoring system to chat bots, all these tech-aids are making the day-to-day task of humans much easier. AI is also making paradigm shifts within academics with its services. Although, the comparison between roles of humans in academics stands nowhere in position with AI teaching due to lack of humanized approach (Fitria, 2021). But still, we must not underestimate the power of AI to bridge the education gap between learned and unlearned. The Fig.1 made below will list some of the AI tools popularly utilized these days in the field of academics.

Fig -1: Source: Authors

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Wadhawan, K., & Kaur, A. AI: Job Creator or Jobless Future (2023). Artificial Intelligence have a wide potential of changing the way, we are working today. We have to prepare ourself for the future wonders of AI in our field of interest. We all have to be ready for the upcoming era of AI soon. Where AI drive our routine and become the part and parcel of our life-style & work system.

Computers and tech-oriented learning is motivating the students to learn well. Intelligent tutoring systems are highly effective in increasing students' performance and motivation. We can design student friendly module which facilitate improved pedagogical learning experience. AI can collaborate in making education more effective and efficient (Beck et al., 1996). Earlier studies had already proved that there is a gross mismatch between in academic curriculum and the actual needs of the industry. The arrival of AI oriented micro credential in tandem with the macro credentials can improve the interaction between academic & industry as a whole (Wadhawan & Wadhawan, 2024a).

According to Malakar et al. (2024) the academic realm is growing really fast with AI. The active integration of AI with the NLP (Natural Language Processing) along with its humanization has led to the academic & scholarly endeavors. Globally there are vast variety of generative AI tool in application that individually these AI tools hold the user base market share in millions. From working professionals to marketers to students to companies forms the customer base of these AI tools. The study analysis of Generative AI collaboration content creation tools find Grammarly as a frontrunner tool in generating collaborative content creation. As the demand for the AI-generated content creation increases, gigantic improvement can be observed in these AI tools as well. Professionals, researchers and other academic stakeholders can harness full potential of these AI tools in the field of content creation in the days to come.

Generative AI technology is producing content on a wide range of topics today. We can use the same in generating big course work, developing learner specific learning outcomes, designing inclusive curriculum. In fact, teachers can also utilize the generative AI technology in making assessment work possible. With generative AI and other like-minded AI tools new horizon opened in the sector of education. Their adoption is welcoming, but condition of ethicality must be must in mind (Ullmann et al., 2024).

The application of generative AI in modern classroom of different course curriculum is welcoming, but we must not forget the fact that any generative AI tools are nowhere equivalent to the human-like human creativity and intuitions. They hold respective limitations and therefore improved research efforts are required while developing AI tools and methods (Hutson & Lang, n.d., 2023).

There exist multiple ethical challenges yet to be addressed while implementing AI in the field of education. More developments are yet to be done to make AI match the specific need of each students (The Future of Learning: AI-guided Content Creation and Automated Delivery Mechanisms, 2024).

2.1 Scope of AI Tools

Humans are surrounded with so many decisions to be taken place every single day Wadhawan and Wadhawan (2024). There is an endless scope of AI in the field of education and learning. From AI Avatar to AI Replace to AI image detector to AI Enhance to AI background to AI Image generator. We have an endless option list available with us, to apply artificial Intelligence in process of improving and enhancing our learning and development system. Considering the immense scope of AI in education, its responsible application is the need of the hour. We have to foster the ethical and responsible use of AI in education (Bilad et al., 2023). Considering the vast scope of AI tools, it is peculiar to note that AI market we had of around \$ 6.4 billion. In fact, government of India is also investing much to foster AI under various flagships Wadhawan and Dimple (2024).

2.2 AI utility for academics stakeholders

For the purpose of convenience of our research study, we have classified the key academic stakeholders into four different heads who may use the Artificial Intelligence as the academics stakeholders.

Fig -2: Source: Authors

2.2.1 Academic Content Creators

There are many AI tools available online, which are used by the academic content creators for grammar check, content curation, fact checking etc. According to Mohamed Khalifa, Mona Albadawy (2024) AI help in different phases of academic content creation including idea generation, structure content, supporting theoretical framework, editing, reviewing, data analysis and management. Tool especially ChatGPT have a wider scope of application in this respective field with adequate balancing with human insights. Some of the popular AI writing assistance tools include- copy.ai, writer, SEOWind, ChatGPT, Jasper, Sudowrite, Buffer's AI Assistance. All these AI tools are useful for generating idea, outlining article, rephrase, shorten content with improving its readability, improving language inclusivity and plagiarism checker and so on. Thus it can be concluded that today, AI tools have a vast utility for the academic content creators.

2.2.2 Faculty Fraternity

According to the report, "Artificial Intelligence and the future of Teaching and Learning" insights and recommendation from Office of Educational Technology (May 2023) (Pg. 25) states that AI assistants can be used to reduce the routine teaching burdens of the teachers. AI can reduce a faculty member's low-level administrative burden. AI can also assist teachers in having student awareness. In fact, AI can work beyond teacher's availability with their students fulfilling teacher's intent even in his absence. Inculcating learning to the tech-savvy student generation demand teachers as well as the faculty fraternity to be tech adopters. Therefore teaching community too are using such powerful AI tools to empower students enjoy learning with technology. Some popular teaching AI aid include – MagicSchoolAI, EduGPT, Curipod, Eduaide, CourseAI, Coursebox, DeepBrainAI, Pictory, Research Rabbit, HumataAI, Speechify, Gamma and Magicslides.

2.2.3 Research Scholars

AI tools are here to stay with us now in this technology era. Therefore, there is a vast scope of AI tools application in the field of research work as well. From data analysis to navigating quality literature review to streamlining the peer-reviewing process, AI has a lot more to do for the service of a research scholar (Arangüena, 2024). Today research scholar make use of some of the popular AI tools such as connected papers, consensus, elicit, keenious, research rabbit, scite, scholarcy, semantic scholar, undermin and so on.

2.2.4 Students

Student group is also one among the major user section of the AI tools. In the age of e-learning and digital education, students also utilized a variety of AI options to make their academic learning easy and interesting. Some of the common AI tools from the students to meet their day-to-day academic needs satisfied are- quillbot, grammarly, chatGPT, turnitin, cognii, khanmigo, canva, gradescope and so on. These AI tools will help students experience personalized learnings, intelligent feedback and bridge their learning gap.

2.3 Humanize AI Tools

Artificial Intelligence will be bringing paradigm shift in every sector. New opportunities will be created in every walk of life. Education policies makers will be adding AI in curriculum of the future learners. A leap and bounce technology revolution is about to come with the advent of AI (Wadhawan & Kaur, 2023). Humanize AI tools are one such revolutionary element of artificial intelligence world.

Humanistic AI focus on using AI in a manner that it will collaborate with AI, instead of replacing humans. Applying humanistic approach of artificial intelligence can become a more beneficial approach for humanity. Adding humanization angle to the AI is welcoming as it could ease the content creation and writing task of the users and help them curate human-styled content in just few seconds. But at the same time, a careful balance needs to be taken care of between ethicality & technological progress. We must humanize AI responsibly (A. Sheth et al, 2024).

Humanizing AI laid the foundation of integrating human intelligence & cognition with the AI development. This particular technology can do wonders, if we utilize this technology using a behavioral lens to bridge the divide between human and machine. The task of humanizing Artificial Intelligence initiate from the perspective of programming stage as the initial step, then training it to behave like anthropomorphism using algorithms. And finally preparing it for organisational as well as the societal level (Fenwick & Molnar, 2022).

2.4 The art of humanizing the AI content

The content generated by the machines so far is suffering from the problem of emotionlessness. But with the introduction of Humanize AI tools and methods, today AI can curate human-like text and messages. The process of creating artificially generated content into human-styled, natural, creativity and emotionally enriched content is called as content humanization. Today many applications and AI tools are available online which can generate humanize AI content. According to GeeksforGeeks (Oct, 2024) some of the best free and paid humanize AI tool are – undetectable AI, humbot, humanize AI, bypass AI, writehuman and stealthGPT. These apps and tools allow replacing generic words with specific synonyms, do adequate sentence structuring, tone adjustments, ensure clarity, add personalization and last but not the least is to avoid AI hallucination means chances of providing incorrect and misleading results by AI. Although, the exact art of humanization of the AI content could be a patent recipe of the AI tool and software companies. But the data shared above is in general understanding sourced from different website shared in references will justify the art of humanization.

2.5 Humanize AI- an Aid or Challenge

Just like, there is always two sides of a coin. Humanize AI tools too have two sides in it. From the utility perspective, Humanize AI can be an aid as well as a challenge for the users. There is no doubt of the fact that Humanize AI is aiding tool for the students, teachers, working professionals, content creators to create human-styled content and can serve for many writing purpose of all of our day-to-day requirements. Today, AI Humanize tools are capable enough to beats and bypass the strictest AI detectors tools like turnitin, GPTZero, and Originality 3.0, ensuring that the writing material remains undetected and unrestricted from the eye of AI.

But we must not forget that this particular technology is still on the process of improvement and evolution. Still conversion of AI generated content into humanized AI generated content didn't guaranteed the foolproof mechanism of having zero percent AI. Scientist and engineers are working on strengthening AI detectors to even detect humanize AI generated content stuff. Thus, partially humanize AI is an aid and partially it's a challenge to be used ahead.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Objectives

- To study the increasing dependence of Humanize AI good or bad for the young generation.
- To understand whether Humanize AI is an aid or challenge for the users.
- To know the user experience towards Humanize AI for content creation & research purposes that too, without AI detection fear.
- To sense the flaws in Humanize AI with respect to its failure from bypass the AI detection test.

3.2 Sampling

The sample was selected using purposive sampling technique. The data was collected from 247 respondents in Uttar Pradesh. The questionnaire instrument was used to collect the data.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

For the purpose of obtaining the fair picture with respect to Humanize AI; a Google-form based questionnaire was made to be filled by the respondents. The questionnaire includes a set of research-specific questions. The total count of respondent is 247. The data analysis of the questionnaire is attached below, with question-relevant charts and figures.

Table -1: Respondent Demographic Information

S.No.	Demographic Information	Demographic Head	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	150	60.728%
		Female	97	39.271%
2.	Age	15-20 Years	206	83.4%
		20-25 Years	38	15.4%
		25-30 Years	1	0.4%
		Above 30 Years	2	0.8%
3.	Occupation	Student	240	97.2%
		Academician/Teacher	9	3.6%
		Corporate Professional	2	0.8%
		Content Creation	5	2%
		Blogger	0	0%
		Others	2	0.8%

Data Interpretation of the Respondent Demographic Information

The table made above (Respondent Demographic Information Table), clearly showcase the Demographic Information of the 247 respondents. We have taken into consideration three different categories i.e. Gender, Age and Occupation within the demographic Information. Each demographic Information is again bifurcated

into respective Demographic Heads. Their respective captured Frequency as well as Percentage is also mentioned against them.

The gender details of our respondents includes – 150 Male respondent (60.728%) and 97 Female respondents (39.271%) participated. We have taken four different age matrix head to classify the respondents in them only. Starting from the age of 15 years, the age bar goes above 30 years. 83.4% of our respondents belongs to the age bracket of 15-20 years. This clearly shows that AI based assistance like Humanize AI is well known to the respondents. Rest 15.4% respondents belong to the age group of 20-25 years. Followed by 0.4% for 25-30 years and 0.8% for above 30 years respectively (Table-1).

When asked about the current occupation in which the respondents were indulged in, the following information makes the picture clear. 97.2% of the surveyed respondents were the students. On the other hand, 3.6% were Academicians, 0.8% were corporate professionals, 2% were content creators and rest 0.8% were belonging to others category respectively. According to our research study, students were among the most active users of AI-based assistance tool i.e. Humanize AI.

Data Analysis/Interpretation as per questionnaire study

Fig -3: Indicate whether the respondents have ever use any AI tool for doing their work. [Source: Authors]

For the purpose of conducting our research study as shown in Fig.3, when asked if they have ever used any Artificial Intelligence tool for doing their work? 229 i.e. 92.7% of the respondent said Yes, whereas just 18 (7.3%) said No. This clearly indicate that a large portion of our study is already using AI in their day-to-day operations.

Fig -4: Indicate the preferred AI-Platform used regularly by the respondents [Source: Authors]

For this question, we have provided nine options of AI platform to choose from. The respondent usually prefer to use the most on regular basis for their content creation needs and other data requirements (Fig.4). The stated results are obtained. 81.8% i.e. (202 respondents) prefer to use Open AI’s ChatGPT, followed by Google’s Gemini with 38.1% i.e. (94 respondents) at the second and Meta platform’s formerly Facebook) Meta AI with 30.4% i.e. (75 respondents) at the third position respectively. Other common AI platforms includes Microsoft Copilot used by 5.3% (13 respondents), others by 4.5% (11 respondents), Oracle AI by 2.8% (7 respondents), Claude by Anthropic by 0.4% (1 respondent) and Dall-E by 0.4% (1 respondent). From our study, it is already clear that ChatGPT is the most commonly used AI platform by the respondents as per Fig. 4

Fig -5: Indicate the purpose of using an AI tool [Source: Authors]

For the purpose of our convenience of study, we have listed eight different areas of AI application (Fig.5). The respondents are not given any open choice of mentioning their AI usage areas. The respondents were supposed to mention their AI tool utility from the given choices only. However the respondents are allowed to answer in multiplicity, as questions allow them to mark more than one option from the stated option list. The result of the study are as follows-

61.9% (153) of the respondents are using AI for doing project work. 59.9% (148) use for doing assignments, 52.6% (130 Respondents) use AI tools for doing research purpose work. 33.2% (82) use AI tools for making presentations, 18.6% (46) for content creation/writing assistance, 13.8% (34 respondents) use it for other purposes, 13% (32 respondents) use it for fun or recreational purposes and finally last 31 respondents i.e. 12.6% use AI tools for article/research paper writing purposes (Fig.5). Although the study results are little confined to eight mentioned options of AI applications only. But in actual life, we may have wider areas to apply and utilize AI tools for doing endless work of different areas like entertainment, critical problem solving, and improving existing fault areas.

Fig -6: Indicate the respondent awareness about Humanize AI tools which are available online [Source: Authors]

After sensing the awareness level of our respondent (sample) group about Artificial Intelligence tools and in which area they use or apply these AI tool for doing what sort of work, we move ahead of asking their awareness with respect to Humanize AI. Since humanize AI is a technology which is capable of converting AI generated content into natural & human language content. 68% i.e. (168 respondents) said Yes, which means they are aware about Humanize AI tools. Whereas 32% i.e. (79 respondents) said No, means they are unaware about this particular tool (Fig.6).

Fig -7: Indicate the Likert scale utility of the humanize AI tools by the respondents [Source: Authors]

When asked about rating their preference from lowest to highest utility with respect to Humanize AI tool, 38.6% i.e. (96 respondents) rate Humanize AI as a useful tool to be used for. Whereas rest 28.3% i.e. (70 respondents) found Humanize AI as moderately useful tool, 19.4% i.e. (48 respondents) found it as Highly useful tool, 6.9% i.e. (17 respondents) as a required tool and rest 6.5% i.e. (16 respondents) found Humanize AI as not required tool as per the data of our study (Fig. 7).

Fig -8: Indicate the respondent’s opinion about ethicality with respect to AI tools [Source: Authors]

We all know to the very fact that AI is eating human jobs. So far, multiple AI tools are assisting us in creating our projects, doing assignments and conducting research papers & article. But every such AI generated content is subject to plagiarism and paraphrasing, as all machine generated content lacks human touch and human language. AI generated content stand nowhere, when compare the same with that with human-originated content which hold shorter sentence length, high perplexity, higher length variation and last but not the least low score on length normality. In such a milieu, converting AI content into Humanize AI hold a question of ethicality? Therefore we want respondents to provide their opinion about Humanize AI tool ethicality perspective. To this question, the respondents so surveyed, 83.4% i.e. (206 Respondents) found it as

an ethical tool. Whereas the rest of the 16.6% i.e. (41 respondents) found it as an unethical tool (Fig.8). In the nutshell, it can be concluded that humanize AI is an ethical technology to be implemented and used.

Fig -9: Indicate the response on whether humanize AI can create better content than human being [Source: Authors]

We asked the respondent to share their opinion about Humanize AI with respect to its ability of creating content better or worse than the human (Fig. 9). Since the process of machine learning have made it easy for the AI to develop human-styled content similarly like human natural language. It leverage the advanced algorithms of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning Technologies to humanize the AI content. For this question to be answered, we have provided a Likert scale with five different heads. The responses so collected are –

45.7% (113 Respondents) believe that Humanize AI can create better content than humans. 15.4% (38 respondents) agree to the fact that humanize AI, can't create better content than humans. 39.3% (97 respondents) believe that Humanize AI can create moderate quality of content than humans. 0.8% (2 respondents) found that humanize AI create inaccurate content and rest 3.2% (8 respondents) believed that humanize AI can create incomplete content on query raised (Fig. 9). Thus as per our research result, majority of the audience found that Humanize AI can create better content than humans.

Fig -10: Record the respondents view point on the question whether Humanize AI tool can replace human cognition and thinking [Source: Authors]

When asked about the possibility, if humanize AI tools can replace the human cognition and thinking process, the following responses appeared out. A majority section (46.5%) i.e. 115 respondent group said that maybe humanize AI tool can replace the human cognition and thinking process, if this particular technology is trained well. The condition of training the humanize AI tool, found the major emphasis here. Rest 22.7% said Yes while 30.8% said No for the humanize AI tool replacing human cognition and thinking (Fig. 10).

Fig -11: Indicate the respondent opinion about whether Humanize AI tools are even bigger challenge from detection point of view, as they are human-like writing stuff [Source: Authors]

There is no doubt of the fact that, today many humanize AI tools are allowing users to bypass the AI detectors and achieve a green signal from the AI detectors of having 100% human-written content. But technology have a solution of every problem. Detection of humanized AI content can be possible using advanced AI detection tools. According to a blog published by Originality.ai, it state that AI still has a very long way to go before it can actually sound authentically like humans.

For the question, does Humanize AI tools are even bigger challenge from detection point of view as they are human-like writing stuff, we provided the responded with three different options of Yes, No and Maybe. 47% (116 respondents) said that may be Humanize AI tool, a bigger challenge from detection point of view. 40.5% (100 respondents) said Yes, which means they believe Humanize AI a challenging tool from detection point of view. While rest 12.6% (31 respondents) said No (Fig. 11). Which means Humanize AI tools is not a challenging tool from detection perspective. Considering the highest respondents count for the “Maybe” option, we can conclude that the detection technology need systematic improvement for detecting humanize AI tool prepared content.

Fig -12: Humanize AI tool is an Aid or Challenge [Source: Authors]

When asked about the defining Humanize AI tool as an Aid or Challenge, 52.2% (129 respondents) found Humanize AI as an aiding technology. On the other hand, 47.8% (118 respondents) found Humanize AI as a challenging technology. Although the percentage of humanize AI tool being aid or challenge is very much cut to cut with the slight margin of (4.4%) respondents calling it as an aid, against the equivalent number of respondent calling it as a challenge (Fig.12).

Fig -13: Indicate Humanize AI tool offer only one-time free access, for further fees is charged, are respondents ready to pay it [Source: Authors]

In the 21st century, every boon of technology is cost-oriented. Just like other AI tools, Humanize AI tools and platforms are also available in subscription fee format. Our intention is to know the proactiveness of the respondents for paying the subscription fee amount for accessing the humanize AI tools for generating human-like content. We presented the respondent with three possible scenarios of first – Paying the subscription fee. Second – Not paying the subscription fee. And third and the last one – They will try any other app or tool next-time which will offer free access to humanize AI tool (Fig.13). 41.7% (103 respondents) wants to try any app or tool next-time to enjoy free access of humanize AI option every time. 39.7% (98 respondents) are not ready to pay the subscription fee for the Humanize AI tool. Whereas a small section of 18.6% (46 respondents) are ready to pay the subscription charges amount for using Humanize AI tools.

Fig -14: Too much dependence on Humanize AI tool is [Source: Authors]

To know the dependence status of Humanize AI tool against pre-decided five different conditions, the following result appears out. The highest count i.e. 35.6% (88 respondents) believe that Humanize AI is a bad technology for our mental cognition ability. Whereas 30.8% (76 respondents) believe that Humanize AI is okay for easing our day-to-day task. 28.3% (70 respondents) found Humanize AI as a good technology which improve the quality of our task work. 17.8% (44 respondents) found Humanize AI as best for saving our time. And lastly, 8.5% (21 respondents) believe that Humanize AI is an unnecessary technology as it deplete our mental intuition (Fig. 14). If we churn out the satisfactory and dissatisfactory portion wrt Humanize AI dependence, we can say that a total of (35.6% + 8.5% i.e.) 44.1% of the total respondent found Humanize AI either bad or unnecessary, rest all the respondents lie in the range of satisfaction with Humanize AI stating it as under okay, good and best options.

Fig -15: Humanize AI can bypass AI detectors, by mimicking human writing [Source: Authors]

Technology such as Humanize AI is already mimicking the writing etiquettes like that of the humans. But to get an impulse from the side of the respondents of our study, we asked the respondents to provide their opinion on whether the Humanize AI tool can bypass the AI detectors by mimicking the human writing methodology. To this 66.8% (165 respondents) said Yes meaning Humanize AI can easily bypass AI detectors? While the rest 33.2% (82 respondents) said No meaning even Humanize AI generated content can be detected by using advanced AI detectors (Fig. 15). However, the responses presents clear picture about bypassing AI, but the results may get changed as AI from both humanization and detection point of view is still evolving.

5. FINDINGS

- Since Artificial Technology as a technology is still evolving and therefore the services which Humanize AI tools are currently offering are subject to rampant modifications in the days to come. Thus calling humanize AI as best or worst tool at this point of time will be a bit early statement.
- If today, content creators, research scholars as well as working professionals are finding humanize AI tools, one of the best mechanism of using AI without AI being known about it (bypassing AI detectors). It would last for few days or months only unless an advanced & foolproof improved AI-based detection mechanism did not buzzed the whole AI market.
- There is actually no comparison between technology & human. Human always be at the positive side of doing all the tech-miracles. Whereas humanize AI is just a glimpse of many such miracles done by man.
- Humanize AI can be used for recurring nature jobs only. Applying its omnipresent application will only deplete the mental cognition ability of humans.

6. CONCLUSION

Humanize AI hold a vast potential in the upcoming future. The upcoming decade will going to thrill us with more and more tech-oriented wonders. May be we will be experiencing many other branches of humanity on AI like emotional AI, sensory AI or spiritual AI. Breakthrough advancement are yet to come in the service of mankind. The future scope of Humanizing AI will not going to be limited to curating human-styled content only. The area could be much vaster to be dive down in this sea bed of AI. Fostering Humanize AI tools advancement to the next level, can let humanize AI to serve human-purpose more naturally. The future of humanize AI is filled with optimistic opportunities. May be AI's humanization can let machines and robot care us as humans, love us as human and guide us as humans. But possibilities are limitless to be envision for. But

man has to be cautioned for balancing this humanize AI technology with the perspective of ethicality and rationality.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE STUDY

This research paper is only centric towards studying the humanize AI tools in relation to content creation and writing stuff generation on the lines of human-styled approach. However, the area of scope for applying humanization in artificial intelligence can be more diversified and vast. We can use humanize AI in the areas other than education, like healthcare, military & defence, research work, waste management, tourism, transportation, domestic help, agriculture and so on. The sky is not the limit. The future research scholars must dive deeper to explore more and address the short comings of this respective research paper. The sample size of the study can be increased. The area of research can be increased to other cities as well.

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